

THE ROLE OF FAMILY VIEWS IN "HUMAN PROPERTY" TODAY

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Annotation: *In the chapter "Family - the Palace of Happiness" in Tahir Malik's "Human Property" about the views and opinions about the family, which is the basis of our society, as well as the evidence and complement of the writer's opinion Our book covers the surahs from the Qur'an, excerpts from the hadiths and exemplary thoughts and quotations of our great thinkers about the family.*

Keywords: *Family, Surah, Hadith, Quote, Society, Marriage.*

“And of His signs is that He created for you mates from yourselves that you may find rest in them, and He has put between you love and mercy. Indeed in that are signs for a people who give thought.”⁵³

(From Surat ar-Rum).

The chapter "Family - the Palace of Happiness" in the book "Human Property" begins with an excerpt from the following surah. There is a sacred place called the family, and everyone, regardless of age, career, good or bad, aspires to that hot spot. In every age, the family has been one of the most important issues, as well as today. Many young people break up their families with a single signature on their divorce papers, leaving their children alone and orphaned. So who is to blame or why? It is strange that such tragic consequences are caused by our young people who do not fully understand the responsibilities of the family, are not spiritually ready for the so-called test of life, do not even think about their duties and responsibilities to the family. . These and similar issues are covered in detail in Tahir Malik's Human Property. If today's young people are familiar with such works, it would be a great light if the families, which are the backbone of the nation and society, flourish day by day.

“.... and live in goodness with them. If you don't like them, don't worry, God will do many good things for you.”⁵⁴

⁵³ T.Malik. "Human property". "Sano-standard". T.: 2018.page-430.

⁵⁴ T.Malik. "Human property". "Sano-standard". T.: 2018.page-431

(From Surat an-Nisa ').

In other words, the author quotes from Surat an-Nisa ': One of the common rights between the two is that when they live together as a family, the couple should live only for the good of each other and do all the good they can. Such a happy lifestyle is commanded by God Himself. According to Islamic teachings, the relationship between a couple should be one of love, affection, compassion and kindness. Therefore, it is not necessary to immediately resort to oppression due to some inconveniences.

In the interpretation of the phrase "... and live in goodness with them" in the verse, we can understand the meaning of the scholar Ibn Kathir, may God have mercy on him: .”

"Men are the guides of women, because Allah has made some of them excel others and spend their wealth."⁵⁵

(From Surat an-Nisa ').

That is, every society needs a leader. Without a leader, there can be no order, no peace, no prosperity. According to Islamic teachings, the family is the most important society and is the cornerstone of a large society. Just as a brick building is strong, so is a strong family. A family that is such an important institution cannot be without a leader.

Why is family leadership given to the man in Islam? The answer to this question is given in the above verse. In fact, a man is created to be the head of the family in terms of his physical structure, inner and outer appearance, mental and other aspects. In addition, the husband bears all the expenses of building and maintaining a family. He thinks that the wealth he has earned through hard work should not be wasted, and he will have to take measures to keep the family strong. For example, if a husband is the head of the family and carries out his leadership as prescribed in the Shari'ah, and such families are blessed, then such families are blessed. . Unfortunately, many people saw the guidance in the verse as an opportunity for anger, oppression, and cruelty. In fact, leadership is a responsibility. Even when there is a responsibility, it is a huge responsibility. According to this responsibility, the husband must take care of the family, including the woman, and take care of her.

He is also the head of the family because he is a man. He sacrifices himself when necessary to protect the family, and bears all the burdens typical of men. He provides for the family, shows kindness and compassion to family members They have no right to oppress or oppress.

⁵⁵ T.Malik. "Human property". "Sano-standard". T. : 2018.page-433

“Be careful. You are all leaders and you are questioned by your subordinates. The imam above the people is the leader and he is questioned by those under him. A man is the leader of his family and he is asked about his subordinates. The woman is the leader in the house of her husband and (her) son, and she will be questioned by her subordinates .”⁵⁶

In other words, in Islam, being a housewife is a great honor, but also a great responsibility. The economy of the family depends on the aunt's thrift, her ability not to betray and squander the means of subsistence entrusted to her. Muslim women have always fulfilled this responsibility with honor. In short, the responsibility of a Muslim woman in the family is incomparable. No one can deny the role of a woman in the success of her husband's work.

"It's just a matter of every Muslim woman fully realizing her responsibility."⁵⁷

"The wives of Imam Ali (ra) saw Fatimah Zahra, the daughter of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him), pale and exhausted, and asked, 'What happened to you, Fatima?' Our mother Fatima said, 'There is no food in the house for three days.' Imam Ali said, 'Then why not tell me?' They said, 'On the day of our wedding, my father, the Messenger of Allah, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, said, 'O Fatima! If Ali finds something, eat it, if not, don't ask. "⁵⁸

A good wife is the state and happiness of the family. The freedom of the house is from him, the calmness and serenity of the landlord is from him. When it is beautiful, it is kind, and when it is kind, it is nourishing.

But, God forbid, if you meet an unfaithful wife, you will have a catastrophic defect in your home. If he is weak, if he is weak, if his heart is hurt and if he seeks evil, then his soul suffers. When the tongue is bitter, it hurts everyone; If it is not clean, it will make her face black. If he is an alcoholic, his house will be ruined, and if he is immoral, his family will be disgraced.

"Very few good wives are born. Whoever meets such a woman is a lucky bird."⁵⁹

"On the Day of Judgment, the first thing a wife will be asked to do is pray, and then the right of rein."

(Reception News)

In conclusion, Tahir Malik's book "The Property of Humanity" contains didactic ideas that can serve as a model for today's youth. , excerpts from the hadiths, exemplary thoughts from the great mashayiks. It would be great if young people on the threshold of life today could read this work.

⁵⁶ T.Malik. "Human property". "Sano-standard". T. : 2018.page-434

⁵⁷Mahmud ibn Muhammad. "Odob ul-muzyfin va zodul-akiliyn". T. : 2011.page-55

⁵⁸ Thensource.page-437

⁵⁹ A.Navoiy. "Mahbub ul-qulub". T. : 2018.page-78

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